

Characterization of Acetogenic and Methanogenic Leachates Generated from a Sanitary Landfill Site

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Abstract—Decomposition processes take place in landfill generate leachates that can be categorized mainly of acetogenic and methanogenic in nature. BOD:COD ratio computed in this study for a landfill site over a 3 years duration revealed as a good indicator to identify acetogenic leachate from methanogenic leachate. Correlation relationships to predict pollutant level taking into consideration of climatic condition are derived.

Keywords—Acetogenic Leachate, Methanogenic Leachate, BOD:COD Ratio.

I. INTRODUCTION

LANDFILLS are major sources of groundwater and land contamination that can cause adverse impacts to the environment. Perforation of pollutants due to waste disposal which passes through as leachate if not properly handled will diffuse through the landfills and contaminate soils and groundwater if left unchecked. The constituents of leachate can be categorized into four types namely organic matter, inorganic matter, heavy metal and xenobiotic organic compounds [1].

The extent of contamination from the leachate depends on the type of control measures used in landfill. Nevertheless, pollutants in the leachate of different composition have different impacts on the environment. Even under controlled conditions such as those of a well planned and well managed landfill, leachate may percolate or penetrate through natural ground and may still contaminate groundwater and ultimate contaminate fresh water supplies over time. The environmental impact is most significant particularly those landfills without integration of engineering controls such as liners and leachate collection system.

The content of leachate generated from most landfill is subject to several factors such as climatic condition, infiltration and waste type. As leachate percolates through waste strata layers that undergo various decomposition high amounts of both organic matter and inorganic matters are found to be higher than those in groundwater [2]-[3].

Both temperature and water content in landfill will affect the rate of waste decomposition which is usually lower in dry

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weather condition. Dissolved organic matter in leachate consists of various organic and inorganic constituents. Higher organic matter is anticipated in acetogenic phase whereas inorganic matter is lower in methanogenic phase due to lower dissolved organic matter and higher pH [4]-[8].

Leachate content generated from waste landfill can be broadly categorized as organic matters, inorganic matter, xenobiotic organic compounds and other compounds due to various conditions such as weather, infiltration, gravity drainage and groundwater inflow. The strength of leachate is depend on decomposition processes comprising of biological and chemical reactions which vary from pH and high concentration of biodegradable organic pollutant in early methanogenic phase to high pH and lower concentration of biodegradable organic content in later methanogenic phase.

The purpose of this paper is to study the impact of temperature and precipitation on landfill performance that yield various pollutant removal experiencing both acetogenic and methanogenic phases.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

Performance data from a landfill site in Toronto, Canada was evaluated over a period of 3 years to assess the range of pollutant in the leachate. The performance data is depicted in Table 1.

The dissolved organic matters were evaluated in terms of BOD (Biochemical Oxygen Demand), COD (Chemical Oxygen Demand) and DOC (Dissolved Organic Carbon). The inorganic matters such as ammonia, calcium, chloride, iron, magnesium, sodium and sulfate of the landfill leachate were evaluated and xenobiotic organic compounds such as phenols were also evaluated. Statistical study using regression analysis to establish correlation relationship to evaluate pollutants from landfill that are leached out from this traditional waste landfill using clay liner taking into consideration of basic properties and factors influencing landfill performance include climatic conditions such as temperature and precipitation and also the organic content of leachate in terms of BOD:COD ratio.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

As water passes through waste strata layer in landfill it triggers and activates decomposition due to present of microorganisms. The decomposition can be defined in two

phases, firstly soluble organic matter produced due to aerobic decomposition or acetogenic phase and secondly methane and carbon dioxide produce due to anaerobic decomposition or methanogenic phase.

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE DATA OF LANDFILL SITE

Parameter	Year	Month	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12		
Temperature	High	1	9	10.5	18.2	25	27.5	31.8	30.5	29.9	29.1	27.2	15	10		
		2	18	7.3	12.9	26	28.8	30.6	35.5	34	33	32.1	28.1	19.1	14	
		3	10	6	16	17	33	33	34	36	27	22	16	11	12	
		4	11	4	15	25	29	34	34	35	32	32	15	11	11	
		5	15	6	13	21	24	31	31.4	31.3	29.4	29.7	21.4	17.4	11	
		6	17	19	30.1	7	2	6.8	11.4	9.3	5.5	6.7	4.6	-4		
		7	24.2	15	14.2	0	0.4	22.1	12.4	11	6.4	20.1	-13.3	-15.2		
		8	13	13	19	4	4	11	11	11	5	5	5	5	10	
		9	17	20	22	7	4	7	12	11	5	5	9	11		
		10	17	18.2	13.4	3.4	4	10.1	12.9	10.9	5.1	2.1	9.6	12.4		
		11	20.5	22.5	43.2	62.4	62.4	93	97.5	123.1	123	123	25.20	25	20	
		Precipitation	1	21	69.90	38.30	98.30	14.90	22.50	18.50	19.40	24.30	46.30	104.80	60.10	
2	45.6		45.5	55.9	64.0	66.0	68.9	36.6	36.2	41.2	61.0	20.3	65.5			
3	45.5		45.5	55.9	64.0	66.0	68.9	36.6	36.2	41.2	61.0	20.3	65.5			
4	45.6		45.5	55.9	64.0	66.0	68.9	36.6	36.2	41.2	61.0	20.3	65.5			
5	45.6		45.5	55.9	64.0	66.0	68.9	36.6	36.2	41.2	61.0	20.3	65.5			
6	0.80		0.15	0.55	0.22	0.15	0.08	0.04	0.06	0.10	0.13	0.10	0.16			
7	0.23		0.11	0.14	0.09	0.13	0.09	0.12	0.08	0.21	0.29	0.29	0.13			
8	0.58		0.12	0.49	0.38	0.38	0.34	0.06	0.06	0.14	0.06	0.11	0.11			
9	0.22		0.12	0.14	0.10	0.12	0.11	0.02	0.32	0.32	0.32	0.22	0.22			
Performance Data	Alkalinity		1	2500	2500	1600	3800	3400	2500	1200	1200	1100	2500	2500	2500	2500
			2	2400	2700	3100	3100	3400	3300	4700	3300	2700	3300	3300	3300	3300
			3	1200	2000	1500	2300	2400	2000	2000	2000	2000	2000	2000	2000	2000
		4	1700	1400	1400	2200	3100	3100	3400	3000	3000	3000	3000	3000	3000	
		5	2800	3200	2500	2200	2400	2400	1900	1200	1200	1300	3300	3300	3300	
		6	200	200	180	200	340	300	450	370	290	6	6	6	6	
		7	200	200	180	200	340	300	450	370	290	6	6	6	6	
		8	120	212	170	240	240	190	220	240	240	180	180	180	180	
		9	140	150	110	200	200	110	120	140	120	200	200	200	200	
		10	300	330	280	210	220	215	299	125	119	92	86	148	148	
		11	120	31	31	38	110	31	35	30	31	180	30	120	120	
		12	120	120	1000	120	110	67	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	
COD	1	480	480	410	640	1000	960	800	1000	1000	1300	490	850			
	2	150	120	140	550	1200	1200	1200	1200	1200	1200	1200	1200	1200		
	3	420	720	540	680	840	720	500	720	570	600	610	570			
	4	380	450	890	890	3160	220	850	1000	1500	990	1260	1000	930		
	5	2200	1200	1100	1100	1400	1400	1400	1400	1400	1400	1400	1400	1400		
	6	150	150	150	300	150	170	107	117	117	117	210	170	243		
	7	240	253	441	411	397	275	207	172	225	6	6	6	6		
	8	280	150	112	152	89	112	148	141	141	141	20.8	139	139		
	9	433	144	177	266	225	154	110	110	146	125	120	112	112		
	10	1020	120	135	148	140	270	162	138	263	213	213	127	105		
	11	580	250	440	480	960	1060	610	579	579	579	579	579	579		
	12	677	618	719	640	976	800	1160	630	581	6	6	6	6		
Chloride	1	500	572	449	632	681	688	515	648	543	584	580	280	280		
	2	450	360	310	460	790	791	811	810	750	580	520	590	590		
	3	830	950	687	620	868	814	720	638	621	619	384	548	548		
	4	640	640	640	640	640	640	640	640	640	640	640	640	640		
	5	320	340	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320		
	6	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450		
	7	450	560	450	470	570	570	570	570	570	570	570	570	570		
	8	320	340	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320		
	9	770	840	440	580	750	430	540	370	390	390	390	390	390		
	10	1200	150	150	200	380	340	280	220	220	220	220	220	220		
	11	300	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320		
	12	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110		
Conductivity	1	520	520	520	520	520	520	520	520	520	520	520	520	520		
	2	520	520	520	520	520	520	520	520	520	520	520	520	520		
	3	450	560	450	470	570	570	570	570	570	570	570	570	570		
	4	320	340	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320		
	5	770	840	440	580	750	430	540	370	390	390	390	390	390		
	6	1200	150	150	200	380	340	280	220	220	220	220	220	220		
	7	300	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320		
	8	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110		
	9	520	520	520	520	520	520	520	520	520	520	520	520	520		
	10	820	900	762	882	864	914	1010	630	560	560	560	560	560		
	11	1020	1140	210	1520	1360	1300	1560	840	690	6	6	6	6		
	12	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140		
Iron	1	140	770	870	1340	1200	1000	930	1050	940	940	970	740			
	2	3720	960	960	890	1230	880	740	1020	890	270	220	220			
	3	1470	237	440	440	440	440	440	440	440	440	440	440			
	4	1470	237	440	440	440	440	440	440	440	440	440	440			
	5	247	24	4.4	3.3	1.0	2.2	2.1	0.9	8.4	1.9	2.67	4.5			
	6	110	140	80	80	140	114	104	112	81	140	121	108			
	7	110	140	80	80	140	114	104	112	81	140	121	108			
	8	110	140	80	80	140	114	104	112	81	140	121	108			
	9	97.6	84.2	77.5	88	107	86	101	75	67	57	59.4	64			
	10	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140			
	11	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140			
	12	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140			
Magnesium	1	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.55	-1	-0.3	-0.5	-0.3	-1	-0.5	-0.5	-0.3			
	2	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.55	-1	-0.3	-0.5	-0.3	-1	-0.5	-0.5	-0.3			
	3	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.55	-1	-0.3	-0.5	-0.3	-1	-0.5	-0.5	-0.3			
	4	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.55	-1	-0.3	-0.5	-0.3	-1	-0.5	-0.5	-0.3			
	5	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.55	-1	-0.3	-0.5	-0.3	-1	-0.5	-0.5	-0.3			
	6	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.55	-1	-0.3	-0.5	-0.3	-1	-0.5	-0.5	-0.3			
	7	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.55	-1	-0.3	-0.5	-0.3	-1	-0.5	-0.5	-0.3			
	8	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.55	-1	-0.3	-0.5	-0.3	-1	-0.5	-0.5	-0.3			
	9	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.55	-1	-0.3	-0.5	-0.3	-1	-0.5	-0.5	-0.3			
	10	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.55	-1	-0.3	-0.5	-0.3	-1	-0.5	-0.5	-0.3			
	11	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.55	-1	-0.3	-0.5	-0.3	-1	-0.5	-0.5	-0.3			
	12	0.55														

waste due to high temperature that facilitates both biological and chemical reaction inside the mass.

Fig. 2 Physical Properties of Leachate Versus Temperature

Fig. 3 Dissolved Organic Matters of Leachate Versus Temperature

Fig. 4 Inorganic Matters of Leachate Versus Temperature

Fig. 5 Xenobiotic Organic Compounds of Leachate Versus Temperature

Figures 6 to 9 depict the correlation relationship of leachate concentration to precipitation. Results illustrate that all physical properties ($r > 0.114$) except pH ($r = 0.077$); all dissolved organic matters ($r > 0.257$); all inorganic matters ($r > 0.118$) except ammonia ($r = 0.077$) and xenobiotic organic compound of phenol ($r = 0.339$) are relatively quite correlated to precipitation as excessive precipitation is likely to slow down decomposition rate in the waste environment which leachate is percolated through.

BOD:COD ratio is also evaluated to established the correlation relationship to leachate concentration obtained from the landfill. Figures 10 to 13 depict the correlation relationship of leachate concentration to BOD:COD ratio.

Results reveals that all physical properties ($r > 0.146$) except total suspended solid ($r = 0.045$); dissolved organic matters ($r > 0.633$); inorganic matter ($r > 0.118$) except iron ($r = 0.063$) and xenobiotic organic compound ($r = 0.688$) are correlated significantly to BOD:COD ratio computed for the leachate concentration obtained for the landfill in this study.

Fig. 6 Physical Properties of Leachate Versus Precipitation

Fig. 7 Dissolved Organic Matters of Leachate Versus Precipitation

Fig. 8 Inorganic Matters of Leachate Versus Precipitation

Fig. 9 Xenobiotic Organic Compounds of Leachate Versus Precipitation

Fig. 10 Physical Properties of Leachate Versus BOD:COD Ratio

Fig. 12 Inorganic Matters of Leachate Versus BOD:COD Ratio

Fig. 11 Dissolved Organic Matters of Leachate Versus BOD:COD Ratio

Fig. 13 Xenobiotic Organic Compounds of Leachate Versus BOD:COD Ratio

IV. CONCLUSION

The study concluded that in an actively decomposing waste landfill, leachate generated can be characterized as acetogenic and methanogenic and BOD:COD ratio of leachate is a good indicator to illustrate the degree of stabilization in landfill. The BOD:COD ratio of leachate computed indicate if sufficient biological and chemical decomposition as well as biodegradation are carried out under changing ambience conditions in the landfill body. It is referred that decreasing BOD:COD ratio is taken as an indicator of degradation of organic substrate due to decomposition.

Acetogenic leachates are typically characterized by its high BOD value and high BOD:COD ratio due to rapid hydrolysis of insoluble organic matters that make it readily degradable. On the other hands, methanogenic leachates are characterized by its relatively low BOD values and low ratios of BOD:COD due to the active dissolution of soluble organic matters present as well as inorganic matter, sulphate, chloride and calcium.

The study also reveals that the waste decomposition in landfill is influenced by climatic condition such as temperature and precipitation based on correlation relationship established. The intensity of decomposition is observed to be significantly affected by amount of precipitation and the temperature inside the landfill mass. Rises in temperature accelerate decomposition while precipitations slow down decomposition to anaerobic condition.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Barlaz, M.A, Schaefer, D.M., and Ham, R.K., Bacterial Population Development and chemical Characteristics of Refuse Decomposition in a Simulated Sanitary landfill, *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.*, 55, 55, 1989a.
- [2] Assumuth, T.W. and Strandberg, T., Ground-water contamination at Finnish landfills. *Water, Air Soil Pollut.*, 69, 179, 1993.
- [3] Kjeldsen, P. and Christophersen, M., Composition of leachate from old landfills in Denmark, *Waste Manag. Res.*, 19, 24-256, 2001.
- [4] Barlaz, M.A., Ham, R.K. and Shaefer, D.M., Methane Production from Municipal Refuse : A Review of Enhancement Techniques and Microbial Dynamics, *CRC Crit. Rev. Environ. Contr.*, 19, 6, 557, 1990
- [5] Kjeldsen, P., Barlaz, M., Rooker, A., Baun, A., Ledin, A. and Christensen, T., Present and Long-Term Composition of MSW Landfill Leachate : A Review. *Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology*, 32, No. 4, 2002.
- [6] Chian, E.S.K., and DeWalle, F.B., Characterization of Soluble organic matter in leachate. *Environ Sci. Technol.*, 11, 158, 1977.
- [7] Ehrig, H.-J., quality and quantity of sanitary landfill leachate, *Waste Manag. Res.*, 1, 53, 1983.
- [8] Martensson, A.M., aulin, C, Wahlberg, O., and Argen, S., Effect of humic substances on the mobility of toxic metals in a mature landfill, *Waste Manag. Res.*, 17, 296, 1999.
- [9] Ritzkowski M., Heyer, K.-U, Stegmann, R. (2003) : Insitu aeration of Old landfills : Carbon Balances, temperatures and settlements. *Proceedings of Sardia, 2003-Ninety International Waste Management and landfill Symposium, Cagliari, Italy, 06-10.10.2003.*